

哈爾濱工程大學
HARBIN ENGINEERING UNIVERSITY

Progress of

Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics:

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About SPHERIC

SPHERIC is the international organisation representing the community of researchers and industrial users of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH). The SPHERIC workshop is the only global event focusing exclusively on the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) methodology and related simulation approaches.

As a purely Lagrangian technique, SPH enables the simulation of highly distorting fluids and solids. Fields including free-surface flows, solid mechanics, multi-phase, fluid-structure interaction and astrophysics where Eulerian methods can be difficult to apply represent ideal applications of this meshless method.

The SPH method was developed to study non-axisymmetric phenomena in astrophysics in the 1970s, but its application to engineering emerged in the 1990s and early 2000s. In the past twenty years the method has developed rapidly in many fields of application from impacts and fracture to breaking waves and fluid-structure interaction.

Following the impulse generated by a collection of local initiatives in 2005 (France, UK, Italy...), a need to foster and collaborate efforts and developments was identified. Since then, the SPHERIC organisation has gone on to push the development of the method forward providing a network of researchers and industrial users around the world as a means to communicate and collaborate.

For more information about SPHERIC, please visit <http://spheric-sph.org>.

SPHERIC Harbin 2020

You are cordially invited to attend the 2020 SPHERIC Harbin International Workshop (SPHERIC Harbin 2020) to be held at Harbin Engineering University (HEU) in Harbin, China, during January, 13-16, 2020. This is the second time that the workshop is held outside of Europe following the SPHERIC Beijing Workshop.

The workshop is aimed at sharing the latest theoretical developments and practical applications of the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics method. All articles on algorithm innovation and engineering applications of SPH method are welcomed.

On behalf of the organizing team, it is our honour to warmly welcome scholars and students from all over the world to attend this workshop in Harbin, and we wish you a happy and satisfactory experience in communicating, training and studying here.

For more information about SPHERIC Harbin 2020, please visit <http://spheric.hrbeu.edu.cn/>.

About Harbin Engineering University

General Information

Harbin Engineering University (HEU) sits at the scenic Songhua River in the ice city of Harbin in Northeast China. Subordinate to the Commission of Science, Technology and Industry for National Defense, HEU is a national key university of glorious history and fine traditions. It was selected to be among the first batch of "211 Project" universities that are entitled to enjoy first priority from the state in construction and development and also one of the universities that have a Graduate School. Moreover, HEU is an important base for talent cultivation and scientific research in the fields of ship industry, marine equipment, marine engineering and nuclear application. HEU encourages students to uphold and carry forward the legacy of the older generation of revolutionaries who advocate "the military spirit" of the original Harbin Institute of Military Engineering. This spirit is condensed to the school motto "academic excellence-pursuit of truth" and forms the core school values: loyalty, fortitude, solidarity, creativity.

HEU has always attached great importance to the tradition of scientific research. The school is well-known not only for the first experimental submarine, the first hydrofoil craft, the first shipboard computer, the first swath bathymeter set and dozens of other major gap-filling scientific research breakthroughs, but also for being the best in the world with several achievements such as duplex submersible vehicles, hovercrafts and gradient velocimeters. The university maintains strong technical knowledge in the shipping, ocean and nuclear fields. Its underwater robots, shipping anti-rolling technology, integrated navigation, acoustic positioning and nuclear power simulation have occupied advanced domestic and international positions, leading HEU to become one of the main forces in the basic and applied research of China's ship science and technology. It is renowned for providing key units of the navy's advanced technical equipment and being a reliable resource for developers of high-techmarine equipment in China.

History

In 1953, the predecessor of HEU, the PLA Military Engineering Institute was established, and Senior General Chen Geng acted as the first president. Chairman Mao gave the instructions for the establishment. According to the types of the services, the Institute was subdivided into five parts: Department of Air Force Engineering, Department of Artillery Engineering, Department of Naval Force Engineering, Department of Armored Forces Engineering, and Department of Corps Engineering. In 1961, the PLA Military Engineering Institute was defined as a national key institute. In April of 1994, the school was renamed as Harbin Engineering University (HEU). In August of 1996, HEU was listed as one of the key universities being enhanced by the first batch of the '211 Project'. In 2002, the Graduate School of HEU was approved for review by the State Council. HEU Intelligent Underwater Robot Lab was listed as a National Key Lab. In 2002, the Ministry of Science and Technology and Ministry of Education approved the construction of a national University Science Park within HEU. In December of 2002, the Commission of Science Technology and Industry for National Defense and the People's Government of Heilongjiang Province signed an agreement to jointly construct this university. In 2011, HEU was listed on the Major course pioneering platform. In 2017, the shipbuilding and ocean engineering discipline was selected into the country's construction plan of world-class universities and first-class disciplines, namely the "double first-class initiative". In 2018, through the international discipline assesment, experts gave the assesment of "one of the strongest program in the world".

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Preface

The Harbin Engineering University is delighted to host the 2020 SPHERIC Harbin International Workshop (or SPHERIC Harbin 2020). This is an important event of 2020 in the field of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) and related particle-based methods.

The SPH European Research Interest Community (SPHERIC) workshop is the only global event focusing exclusively on the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) methodology and related simulation approaches. It aims at encouraging and facilitating the spread of the method throughout Europe and the wider international community. The SPHERIC community plays an important role in helping the development of SPH for academia, industry and government organizations. SPH is one of the most exciting new areas in the field of computational methods and is opening up the possibility of research into fields that were beyond any modelling capability.

The SPHERIC Harbin 2020 organization committee received abstracts from China, France, Germany, UK, Italy, Spain, Switzerland, Ireland, USA, Canada, Japan and Australia, while more than 50 papers were selected to present in the SPHERIC Harbin 2020. This demonstrates just how active the field is, with works ranging from traditional hydrodynamics to solids, fluid-structure interaction, high performance computing and industrial applications.

Harbin is one of the eighth most populous Chinese cities and the largest city in the northeastern region of China. Harbin serves as a key political, economic, scientific, cultural, and communicational hub in Northeast China, as well as an important industrial base of the nation. We warmly welcome scholars and students from all over the world to attend this workshop in Harbin, and wish you a happy and satisfactory experience in communicating, training and studying here.

It is a great pleasure to welcome you to Harbin, and share a successful and enjoyable meeting with you.

Professor, Harbin Engineering University
Chair, Local Organization Committee
SPHERIC Harbin 2020

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Further improvements of the δ -LES-SPH model

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Abstract—This work presents novel studies and investigations regarding the SPH model presented in [1], where the SPH equations are rewritten within a Large Eddy Simulation (LES) framework. Compared with the original formulation, here the model is recast in a quasi-Lagrangian fashion and the fluid particles are moved by adding to the actual velocity a small deviation based on the Particle Shifting Technique (PST) described in [2]. Moreover, to avoid the formation of voids in the fluid regions characterized by high vorticity and negative pressure, the Tensile Instability Control (TIC) technique presented in [3] is also implemented. The combination of the particle shifting technique with the tensile instability control allows for a stable and robust numerical scheme, which is suited for the simulations of high Reynolds number flows typical of the LES approach. The proposed model is tested within a 2D framework, considering the evolution of a fluid at rest which is forced by an initial time window and, then, left free to evolve, generating freely decaying turbulence. The forcing used in the above problem mimics the formation of the vortex patches of the Taylor-Green problem. The results obtained with the proposed model are going to be compared with the solutions obtained from a Mesh-based Finite Volume Method.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last years an increasing number of papers have been dedicated to the extension of the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) to model problems characterized by turbulent flows [15], [18]–[20]. Among the different approaches, the Large-Eddy-Simulation appears as the most suited method to be included in the SPH framework, being based on a filtering of the Navier-Stokes equations that resembles the one adopted for the derivation of the smoothed differential operators of the SPH. The present work follows the above-mentioned line of research and extends and generalizes the approach described in [1] where a Lagrangian LES-SPH scheme was proposed. Specifically, the proposed scheme is based on the definition of a Quasi-Lagrangian Large-Eddy-Simulation model where a small velocity deviation is added to the actual fluid velocity. This approach allows us to cast the LES in the framework of the most advanced SPH schemes which rely on a quasi-Lagrangian motion of the fluid particles [21], [22]. In particular, when the LES equations are rearranged in the SPH formalism, the velocity deviation is modelled through the Particle Shifting Technique (PST), similarly to the δ plus-SPH scheme derived in [5]. The latter technique proved to be a crucial numerical tool to obtain regular particle distributions, reducing the numerical errors in the evaluation of the spatial differential operators.

The presence of the velocity deviation with respect to the

actual fluid velocity leads to the appearance of additional terms in the continuity and momentum equations of the proposed LES-SPH scheme that need proper turbulence closures. Specifically, the term in the momentum equation is represented through a classical LES closure while that in the continuity equation is modelled through the diffusive term of the δ -SPH scheme (see, for example, [4]).

In addition to PST, the Tensile Instability Control (TIC) described in [3] is included in the formulation to avoid the formation of voids in the fluid regions characterized by high vorticity and negative pressure. The combination of the particle shifting technique with the tensile instability control allows for a stable and robust numerical scheme, which is suited for the simulations of high Reynolds number flows typical of the LES approach.

The paper is organized as follows: section §II briefly introduces the theoretical model and corresponding the numerical scheme and section §III shows the preliminary results.

II. QUASI-LAGRANGIAN δ LES-SPH

Let us consider the Navier-Stokes equations for a barotropic weakly-compressible Newtonian fluid:

$$\begin{cases} \rho_t + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0, \\ \mathbf{u}_t + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = -\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + \nu \Delta \mathbf{u} + (\lambda' + \nu) \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{u}$ is the flow velocity, p and ρ denote the pressure and density fields respectively and are related through a state equation, namely $p = F(\rho)$. The hypothesis that the fluid is weakly-compressible corresponds to assume:

$$\frac{dp}{d\rho} = c^2 \gg \max \left(\|\mathbf{u}\|^2, \frac{\delta p}{\rho} \right), \quad (2)$$

where δp indicates the variation of the pressure field and $c = c(\rho)$ is the sound speed (see e.g. [6], [7]). The viscosity coefficients ν , λ' indicate the ratios between the Lamé constants μ , λ and the density ρ . Since the fluid is weakly-compressible, ν and λ' are assumed constant. Now, let us define a generic filter in $\mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}$ as follows:

$$\phi = \phi(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t) - \mathbf{y}, t - \tau). \quad (3)$$

The above filter is supposed to have a compact support, to depend only on $\|\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t) - \mathbf{y}\|$ and $|t - \tau|$, and to be an even function with respect to both arguments. Here $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t)$ indicates

the position of a *quasi-lagrangian* point that moves in the fluid domain according to the following equation:

$$\boxed{\frac{d\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p}{dt} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t), t) + \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t), t)}, \quad (4)$$

where $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ is a (small) arbitrary velocity deviation (to be specified later) while $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ is given by the following definition:

$$\boxed{\tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t), t) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \phi(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t) - \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{y}, \tau) d\tau dV_{\mathbf{y}}.}$$

Hereinafter, we refer to $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ as the filtered position and velocity, respectively. Accordingly, the main idea is to rewrite the system (1) in terms of the filtered quantities and obtain a quasi-Lagrangian LES scheme. With respect to this point, we observe that, since the state equation is generally nonlinear, $\widetilde{F(\rho)}$ is different from $F(\tilde{\rho})$ and, consequently, the filtering procedure cannot be applied to both pressure and density. To avoid inconsistency, when we refer to *filtered* pressure we mean $\tilde{p} = F(\tilde{\rho})$. Under this hypothesis, we apply the filter in (3) to the Navier-Stokes equations for weakly-compressible flows and, integrating over $\mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}$, we obtain:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d\tilde{\rho}}{dt} = -\tilde{\rho} \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}) + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \widetilde{\rho\mathbf{u}}) + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho}\delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}), \\ \frac{d\tilde{\mathbf{u}}}{dt} = -\frac{\nabla\tilde{p}}{\tilde{\rho}} + \nu\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} + (\lambda' + \nu)\nabla(\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}}) \\ \quad - \nabla \left[\widetilde{G(\rho)} - G(\tilde{\rho}) \right] + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T}_\ell \\ \quad + \widetilde{\mathbf{u}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}} + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \otimes \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}) - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\nabla \cdot \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}), \\ \frac{d\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p}{dt} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \quad \tilde{p} = F(\tilde{\rho}), \quad G(\rho) = \int^{\rho} \frac{1}{s} \frac{dF}{ds} ds, \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d\tilde{\rho}}{dt} = -\tilde{\rho} \langle \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}) \rangle + \langle \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho}\delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}) \rangle \\ \quad + \mathcal{C}_1 + \mathcal{C}_2 + \mathcal{C}_3, \\ \frac{d\tilde{\mathbf{u}}}{dt} = -\frac{\langle \nabla\tilde{p} \rangle}{\tilde{\rho}} + \nu\langle \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle + (\lambda' + \nu)\langle \nabla(\nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}}) \rangle \\ \quad + \langle \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \otimes \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}) \rangle - \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \langle \nabla \cdot \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle \\ \quad + \mathcal{M}_1 + \mathcal{M}_2 + \mathcal{M}_3, \\ \frac{d\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p}{dt} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \quad \tilde{p} = F(\tilde{\rho}), \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

where the total time derivatives d/dt is done with respect to the velocity $\tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ and $\mathbf{T}_\ell = \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \otimes \tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \widetilde{\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}}$. Note that the latter tensor is equivalent to the sub-grid stress tensor. Following the derivation shown in [1], we now rearrange the system (5) in the framework of the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) scheme. To this purpose, we split the filter ϕ into

$$\phi(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t) - \mathbf{y}, t - \tau) = W(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t) - \mathbf{y}) \theta(t - \tau), \quad (6)$$

where W indicates the SPH kernel and denote the spatial and time filtering as below:

$$\langle f \rangle(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t), t) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} W(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p(t) - \mathbf{y}) f(\mathbf{y}, t) dV_{\mathbf{y}}$$

$$\bar{f}(\mathbf{y}, t) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \theta(t - \tau) f(\mathbf{y}, \tau) d\tau.$$

Using the above definitions it is easy to prove that $\tilde{f} = \langle \bar{f} \rangle$ and that, generally, the time and space filters do not commute, i.e. $\langle \bar{f} \rangle \neq \bar{\langle f \rangle}$ (see, for example, [1]). Since the time filter is the inner one, the overall LES-SPH scheme may be regarded as a spatial Lagrangian filter applied to a set of time-averaged

variables. In this sense, the time filter may be thought as an implicit filter whose presence is accounted for through the modeling of the additional terms.

Now, suppose that we want to model a high Reynolds number flow, for which LES filtering is required. Then, we need the filtered variables $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \tilde{p}, \tilde{\rho}$ for each fluid particle at positions $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_p$; at the same time, we want to approximate the operators in equation (5) in the SPH fashion. For example, using the above definitions, we can rearrange the gradient of $\tilde{f}$ as follows:

$$\nabla \tilde{f} = \langle \nabla \cdot \tilde{f} \rangle = \langle \nabla(\bar{f} + \tilde{f} - \bar{f}) \rangle = \langle \nabla \tilde{f} \rangle + \langle \nabla(\bar{f} - \tilde{f}) \rangle,$$

where the first term in the right-hand side is the SPH operator while the latter term accounts for small scale ‘‘fluctuations’’ in space, hereinafter denoted through $f' = \bar{f} - \tilde{f}$. For confined flows, the non-commutability of filtering and differentiation must be taken into account for a rigorous extension of the filtering close to the boundaries (i.e. in those points whose distance from the boundaries is smaller than the kernel radius). The above procedure can be applied to all the remaining operators. By doing so, in SPH formalism the system (5) reads:

where:

$$\mathcal{C}_1 = -\tilde{\rho} \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}' \rangle, \quad \mathcal{C}_2 = \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \widetilde{\rho\mathbf{u}}),$$

$$\mathcal{C}_3 = -\tilde{\rho} \nabla \cdot (\delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \langle \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle) + \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\rho}\delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \langle \tilde{\rho}\delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle),$$

$$\mathcal{M}_1 = -\frac{\langle \nabla p' \rangle}{\tilde{\rho}} + \nu \langle \Delta \mathbf{u}' \rangle + (\lambda' + \nu) \langle \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}') \rangle,$$

$$\mathcal{M}_2 = -\nabla \left[\widetilde{G(\rho)} - G(\tilde{\rho}) \right] + \widetilde{\mathbf{u}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T}_\ell$$

$$\mathcal{M}_3 = \nabla \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \otimes \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \langle \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \otimes \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle) - \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \nabla \cdot (\delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} - \langle \delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle).$$

Here $\mathcal{C}_1$ and $\mathcal{M}_1$ come from the SPH approximation procedure and require a SPH closure, whereas $\mathcal{C}_2$ and $\mathcal{M}_2$ include all terms from the Lagrangian LES and require a LES closure. Finally, $\mathcal{C}_3$ and $\mathcal{M}_3$ come from the use of the generic deviation velocity $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$. Using a Taylor expansion and the hypothesis that the fluid is weakly-compressible, it is possible to show that both $\mathcal{C}_3$ and $\mathcal{M}_3$ are negligible while $\mathcal{C}_1$ and $\mathcal{M}_1$ play a minor

role with respect to the terms $\mathcal{C}_2$ and $\mathcal{M}_2$. As a consequence, only $\mathcal{C}_2$ and $\mathcal{M}_2$ are retained and modelled following a LES closure approach. In particular, $\mathcal{M}_2$ is modelled as done in [1]:

$$\mathcal{M}_2 \simeq \nabla \cdot \left[-\frac{q^2}{3} \mathbf{1} - \frac{2}{3} \nu_T \text{Tr}(\tilde{\mathbf{D}}) \mathbf{1} + 2 \nu_T \tilde{\mathbf{D}} \right], \quad (8)$$

where q^2 represents the turbulent kinetic energy, ν_T is the turbulent kinetic viscosity and $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$ is the strain-rate tensor, that is $\tilde{\mathbf{D}} = (\nabla \tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \nabla \tilde{\mathbf{u}}^T)/2$. Similarly to [14], we assume:

$$q^2 = 2 C_Y \ell^2 \|\tilde{\mathbf{D}}\|^2, \quad \nu_T = (C_S \ell)^2 \|\tilde{\mathbf{D}}\|, \quad (9)$$

where $\|\tilde{\mathbf{D}}\|$ is a rescaled Frobenius norm, namely $\|\tilde{\mathbf{D}}\| = \sqrt{2\tilde{\mathbf{D}}:\tilde{\mathbf{D}}}$ and ℓ is the radius of the SPH spatial kernel. The dimensionless parameters C_Y and C_S are respectively called the Yoshizawa and Smagorinsky constants.

For what concerns $\mathcal{C}_2$, the closure proposed in [1] corresponds to $\mathcal{C}_2 = \nabla \cdot (\nu_\delta \nabla \tilde{\rho})$ where ν_δ is assumed to be a function of $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$. In agreement with the usual approaches adopted in the LES framework, this is equivalent to model $\mathcal{C}_2$ as a diffusive term. In the present work we adopt a finer closure and write:

$$\mathcal{C}_2 = \ell^2 \nabla \cdot (\nu_\delta \nabla \Delta \tilde{\rho}). \quad (10)$$

In the SPH framework a simple way to model $\mathcal{C}_2$ is obtained by using the diffusive term proposed in the δ -SPH model (see [12]), since this contains fourth-order spatial derivatives of the density field.

A. Numerical Scheme

To write the system (5) in the discrete formalism, we rely on the work of Sun et al. [5] where the additional $\delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ -terms are included in the SPH framework in a consistent way. In particular we obtain:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d\tilde{\rho}_i}{dt} = -\tilde{\rho}_i \sum_j [(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_j + \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_j) - (\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i + \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i)] \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \\ \sum_j (\tilde{\rho}_j \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_j + \tilde{\rho}_i \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \sum_j \delta_{ij} \psi_{ji} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{d\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i}{dt} = \frac{\rho_0}{\tilde{\rho}_i} K \sum_j \alpha_{ij} \pi_{ij} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j - \frac{1}{\tilde{\rho}_i} \sum_j (\tilde{p}_j + \tilde{p}_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ + \frac{\rho_0}{\tilde{\rho}_i} \sum_j (\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_j \otimes \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_j + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i \otimes \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i \sum_j (\delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_j - \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \frac{d\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i}{dt} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i + \delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i, \quad \tilde{p}_i = F(\tilde{\rho}_i), \quad V_i = \frac{m_i}{\tilde{\rho}_i}, \end{array} \right.$$

where m_i is the i -th particle mass (assumed to be constant) and V_i is its volume while $W_{ij} = W(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j)$. The coefficient

of the viscous term is $K = 2(n+2)$ where n is the number of spatial dimensions while its arguments are:

$$\pi_{ij} = \frac{(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i) \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i)}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i\|^2} \quad \alpha_{ij} = \frac{\mu}{\rho_0} + 2 \frac{\nu_i^T \nu_j^T}{\nu_i^T + \nu_j^T},$$

where $\nu_i^T = (C_S \ell)^2 \|\tilde{\mathbf{D}}_i\|$ and C_S is the Smagorinsky constant (set equal to 0.12). The first contribution in the expression of α_{ij} represents the actual fluid viscosity while the latter one is the LES closure for turbulence. Note that all contributions related to the fluid compressibility have been neglected, since they are negligible in comparison to the leading order stress tensor. The symbol ψ_{ij} is the argument of the diffusive term of [12], namely:

$$\psi_{ij} = \left[(\rho_j - \rho_i) - \frac{1}{2} (\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L + \langle \nabla \rho \rangle_j^L) \cdot (\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i) \right] \frac{(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i)}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i\|^2}.$$

Here the superscript L indicates that the gradient is evaluated through the renormalized gradient formula [11] as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L = \sum_j (\rho_j - \rho_i) \mathbf{L}_i \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \mathbf{L}_i = \left[\sum_j (\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_j - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i) \otimes \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \right]^{-1} \end{array} \right. \quad (11)$$

As done in [1] and in [13], the diffusive term is not multiplied by an external parameter but the latter is included directly inside the summation and modelled as a viscous-like coefficient following a standard LES approach. In particular we choose:

$$\delta_{ij} = 2 \frac{\nu_i^\delta \nu_j^\delta}{\nu_i^\delta + \nu_j^\delta}, \quad \text{where } \nu_i^\delta = (C_\delta \ell)^2 \|\tilde{\mathbf{D}}_i\|. \quad (12)$$

in which C_δ is a dimensionless constant set equal to 6.

As often done for weakly-compressible fluids, the state equation is linearized around the reference density ρ_0 , leading to $\tilde{p}_i = c_0^2 (\tilde{\rho}_i - \rho_0)$ where $c_0 = c(\rho_0)$ is a numerical sound speed that satisfies the following requirement:

$$M_a = \frac{U_{ref}}{c_0} \leq 0.1 \quad \text{with } U_{ref} = \max \left(U_{max}, \sqrt{\frac{\delta \tilde{p}_{max}}{\rho_0}} \right).$$

Here U_{max} and $\delta \tilde{p}_{max}$ indicate the maximum fluid velocity and the maximum pressure variation expected during the simulation. The above inequality allows the density variations to be below 1% (see [7]).

Finally, following [5], the velocity deviation is defined as:

$$\delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i = \min \left(\|\delta \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i\|, \frac{U_{max}}{2} \right) \frac{\delta \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i}{\|\delta \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i\|} \quad (13)$$

where:

$$\delta \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i = -M_a \ell c_0 \sum_j \left[1 + R \left(\frac{W_{ij}}{W(\Delta x)} \right)^n \right] \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j. \quad (14)$$

and Δx is the initial mean particle distance. Here the constants R and n are set equal to 0.2 and 4 respectively. The expression

in (13) has to be further corrected for particles close to the domain boundaries to avoid a non-physical particle motion. For further details we address the interested reader to [5].

Finally, the Tensile Instability Control (TIC) described in [3] has been implemented in the present model to avoid the onset of tensile instability when the large regions of negative pressure arise in the fluid domain. This corresponds to a simple switch in the formula of the pressure gradient, that is:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{p}_j + \tilde{p}_i & \text{if } \tilde{p}_i \geq 0 \text{ or } i \in \mathcal{S}_F \\ \tilde{p}_j - \tilde{p}_i & \text{if } \tilde{p}_i < 0 \text{ and } i \notin \mathcal{S}_F \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathcal{S}_F$ denotes the region of the fluid domain close to the free surface (if present), that is the free-surface particles and their neighbour particles. The free surface particles are detected through the algorithm described in [23].

III. APPLICATIONS

Here we consider the evolution of a viscous fluid initially at rest which is forced to move by an external body force. The external excitation is applied for a finite time interval up to the onset of turbulence. Then, the fluid is left free to evolve and the freely-decaying turbulence is studied. The body force is obtained from the Taylor vortex solution [24] and mimics the formation of vortex patches inside the fluid domain. Its expression at the position of the i -th particle is given below:

$$\begin{cases} F_{1,i} = r(t) A \sin(8\pi\tilde{x}_i) \cos(8\pi\tilde{y}_i), \\ F_{2,i} = -r(t) A \cos(8\pi\tilde{x}_i) \sin(8\pi\tilde{y}_i), \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $r(t)$ is the time ramp:

$$r(t) = \begin{cases} 10t & \text{for } t \in [0, 0.1) \\ 1 & \text{for } t \in [0.1, 0.9) \\ 10(1-t) & \text{for } t \in [0.9, 1) \\ 0 & \text{for } t \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

The amplitude A is set equal to 1.3 so that the maximum expected velocity during the simulation, namely U_{max} , is close to unity. The forcing term in (16) generates a pattern of 8×8 vortex cores in a squared fluid patch of dimensions $L = 1m$ (see the bottom panel of Figure 1). Three values of the Reynolds number are considered for the simulations, namely $Re = U_{max}L/\nu = 10^4, 10^5, 10^6$, while the spatial resolution is set equal to $L/\Delta x = 1200$ for all the cases. The forcing term induces a kinetic energy growth up to $tU/L = 1$ (see the top panel of Figure 1) after which the flow becomes unstable and leads to the onset of freely decaying turbulence.

Before showing the results of the proposed model, we briefly describe the reasons that led us to define a quasi Lagrangian LES-SPH scheme. When we use a Lagrangian LES-SPH model as, for example, that described in Di Mascio et al. [1], the simulation of the high Reynolds number problems represents a great challenge. In particular, the occurrence of regions with large negative pressure values leads to the onset of the so-called tensile instability and to the consequent generation of voids inside the fluid domain. In the SPH framework (and for confined flows) this issue is

Fig. 1. Forced Taylor vortex motion. Top panel: time history of the kinetic energy for different Reynolds numbers. Bottom: snapshot of the horizontal velocity component at $tU/L = 1$.

usually avoided by introducing a background pressure in such a way that, during the whole evolution, the pressure field always maintains positive. Unfortunately, this strategy induces some short-length oscillations (due to particle resettlement) that affect both the pressure and velocity fields and that lead the energy spectrum to deviate from the theoretical decay. This behaviour is briefly summarized in Figure 2 where the top panel displays a snapshot of the kinetic energy field at $tU/L = 3$ and the bottom panel shows the corresponding energy spectrum. The deviation from the theoretical rate of decay occurs at wave lengths that are comparable with the kernel radius (in Figure 2 the corresponding wave number is denoted by k_R while that associated with the initial forcing is indicated by k_f). In this case, the use of the Tensile Instability Control (TIC) instead of the pressure background leads to even worse results, since the pressure field becomes completely unstructured (see Figure 3).

The results shown above convinced us about the necessity of including the TIC along with Particle Shifting Technique

Fig. 2. Model of Di Mascio et al. (2017) with pressure background for $Re = 10^6$ and $L/\Delta x = 1200$. Top panel: snapshot of the kinetic energy field at $tU/L = 3$. Bottom panel: energy spectrum at the same time. Symbols k_f and k_R indicate the wave numbers of the external forcing and the kernel radius respectively.

(PST) described in [5] in the δ -LES-SPH scheme in order to get rid of the tensile instability and, at the same time, to obtain a regular particle distribution and a consequent reduction of the spurious noise. This led to the derivation of the quasi-Lagrangian scheme described in Section §II.

The behaviour of the proposed δ -LES-SPH model is summarized in Figure 4 where the energy spectra at $tU/L = 3$ are displayed for different Reynolds numbers along with the wave numbers related to the forcing term (i.e. k_f) and to the kernel radius (that is, k_R). Apart from the case at $Re = 10,000$

Fig. 3. Model of Di Mascio et al. (2017) with Tensile Instability Control (TIC) for $Re = 10^6$ and $L/\Delta x = 1200$. Snapshot of the pressure field at $tU/L = 1.44$.

where a slight deviation from the theoretical profile is observed close to k_R , the remaining simulations show a good agreement with the direct and inverse cascades for turbulence in 2D. In particular the case at $Re = 10^6$ (bottom panel Figure 4) also displays a comparison with the energy spectrum obtained from a Finite-Volume scheme, further confirming the reliability of the present δ -LES-SPH model. In this latter case, we also drew the positions of the wave numbers k_λ and k_D related to the Taylor and Kolmogorov scales, that is:

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{10\nu\mathcal{E}}{\epsilon}}, \quad \eta = \left(\frac{\nu^3}{\epsilon}\right)^{1/4}, \quad (18)$$

where ϵ is the rate of energy dissipation and $\mathcal{E}$ is the kinetic energy (the flow is assumed to be fully turbulent). Generally, the length scales which are larger than the Taylor microscale are not strongly affected by viscosity while, on the contrary, length scales smaller than the Kolmogorov microscale are completely dissipated by viscous effects. In particular, these scales are used to identify the inertial range of turbulence. For the case at $Re = 10^6$ the fact that the Kolmogorov scale is smaller than the minimum simulated length and the Taylor scale is close to the length of the forcing term confirms that the LES simulation is correctly applied. Some snapshots of the kinetic energy and vorticity fields for this latter case are displayed in Figure 5.

IV. CONCLUSION

Further improvements of the δ -LES-SPH model described in Di Mascio et al. [1] have been described. In particular, a quasi-Lagrangian formulation of the LES filtering procedure has been implemented and tested against an initially forced motion

Fig. 4. Energy spectra at $tU/L = 3$ for different Reynolds numbers (the spatial resolution is $L/\Delta x = 1200$ for all the cases). Symbols k_f and k_R indicate the wave numbers of the external forcing and the kernel radius respectively while k_χ and k_D are the wave numbers associated with the Taylor and Kolmogorov scales.

Fig. 5. Present model for $Re = 10^6$ and $L/\Delta x = 1200$. Snapshots of the kinetic energy (top) and vorticity fields (bottom) at $tU/L = 3$.

that resembles the Taylor vortex solution and a consequent transition to freely-decaying turbulence.

Thanks to the easy and straightforward inclusion of the Particle Shifting Technique and the Tensile Instability Control, the proposed model overcomes some of the well-known issues that affect SPH simulations of high Reynolds number flows, as the generation of high-frequency spurious noise and the onset of the tensile instability. The comparisons of the energy spectra with the theoretical rate of decay confirm the accuracy and reliability of the proposed quasi-Lagrangian scheme.

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